

THE ESSENCE OF THE CONTENT OF THE STUDY OF INTEGRATIVE MECHANISMS OF SOCIALIZATION OF CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES

Jiyanberdiev Merojiddin

Teacher of the Department of General psychology, Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7826094>

Abstract. *In the article, the current problems of social adaptation and rehabilitation of disabled children are focused on the inclusion of children in convenient areas of household, individual and socially significant activities, taking into account the personal interests and capabilities of children in a targeted socio-pedagogical impact. The features are also studied in detail teaching integrative mechanisms of socialization of children with disabilities.*

Keywords: *integrative, socialization, disabled person, disabled person mechanism, modern form, content of education, technology, life competence, creative ability.*

In our country, measures are being taken to provide state support for persons with disabilities, provide medical and social assistance, improve the quality of life improvement system, provide them with comprehensive assistance in education and employment. Particular attention is paid by the state to the important needs and requirements of persons with disabilities, taking into account the feelings of kindness and goodness inherent in our people. Therefore, on the basis of pedagogical and psychological approaches to students with limited opportunities, the implementation of systematic work on the development of their educational upbringing, the further formation of professional skills of mature competitive personnel, has become an urgent task. "Supporting children who are deprived of parental affection and have disabilities, raising them as active members of society, requires serious attention and practical actions from all of us. Not a single child should cry "I am an orphan or a disabled person", not be left out of the love of our state and society. It is not only a task, but also a sacred duty to teach them to modern professions, to create all the conditions." President Shavkat Mirziyoev expressed these views at a video director meeting held yesterday on issues of expanding state support for children with disabilities, deprived of parental care and orphans, as well as improving social benefits.

At the meeting, special attention was paid to the issues of support and treatment of children with disabilities. The head of state instructed to provide such children with the necessary medical equipment and strollers, to carry out surgical operations, to provide additional funds for the installation of implants and prostheses. It was also noted that it is possible to improve conditions by attaching large enterprises and clusters to specialized schools. Instead of Juvenile work commissions, a National Commission on children's issues was established, while territorial commissions were headed by provincial governors. The commission on preparation of proposals aimed at radically improving the system of state support for Persons with disabilities, established by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. F-5006 of August 1, 2017, examined the situation of work in the field of early identification and Prevention of disability, medical and social assistance to persons with disabilities, their professional training and employment. This law was adopted by the Legislative Chamber of the Supreme Assembly of Uzbekistan on July 22, 2020 and approved by the Senate on September 11, 2020. As you know,

paragraph 143 of the state program" year for the support of active entrepreneurship, innovative ideas and technologies "defined the task of developing the draft law of the Republic of Uzbekistan"on the rights of Persons With Disabilities". On October 15, 2020, with the signing of the law "on the rights of Persons with disabilities"by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the implementation of this paragraph established in the state program was ensured.

In this regard, both the requirements of the UN Convention on the rights of Persons with disabilities and the application of international standards to national legislation, as well as the use of the concept of "person with disabilities" instead of the concept of " disabled;

- rights of persons with disabilities;
- powers of state bodies in the field of protection of the rights of persons with disabilities;
- identification and prevention of disability, assistance in their education and employment, determination of modern forms and mechanisms of providing medical and social assistance to them;

- it was prescribed to radically improve the methods used in the definition of disability and to provide for other rules. In terms of an active approach to the socialization of children with disabilities, it is necessary to create conditions for children to gradually master the socially significant behavioral experience, the norms of the culture of communication with other people, the culture of morality and labor .

The problems of social adaptation and rehabilitation of children with disabilities are solved in the conditions of targeted socio-pedagogical impact by introducing them into favorable areas of household, individual and socially significant activities, taking into account the personal interests and capabilities of children. The changes taking place in the social life of our country significantly change the objective conditions of socialization of children with disabilities. Work on the socialization of children with disabilities was carried out mainly through the generally accepted system of means of communication. In recent years, thanks to the implementation of the ideas of humanization, democratization in the educational system for children with disabilities, new forms of Education, innovative approaches to Education (G.L.Zaitseva, E.I.Léongard, N.D.Shmatko). T.A. Basilova, E.L. Goncharova, A.G. Zikeev, T.S. Zikova, T.K. Korolevskaya, O.I. Kukushkina and others are devoted to the study of the socio-emotional development of children.

The problem of the social status of the disabled person attracted the attention of a huge number of researchers (V.M. Astapov, O.I. Lebedinskaya, B.Yu.Shapiro, E.F. Achildieva, A.A. Baranov, R.K. Ignatieva, L.K. Grachev , TA Dobrovolskaya, IP Katkova, VV Kuznetsova, SS Kuchinsky, SP Pyapkov, GG Silaste, NB Shabalina, I. A. Shames, S.P. Shevchuk, Yu.G. Ellansky). Nevertheless, the solution to this problem still requires more analysis and understanding.

Modern specialized educational institutions are faced with the problem of looking for ways to improve the education and education of children with disabilities in order to solve important socio-pedagogical problems at a new stage of their development. The attention of specialized educational institutions is aimed at updating the content and technology of education and upbringing, developing vital competence and creative abilities, changing the focus on the social adaptation of children with disabilities.

In this regard, the importance of studying the problem of socialization of children with disabilities is increasing. It should be noted that in the field of Correctional activity of a social educator, when solving problems of children with disabilities, methods of social integration of

such children are poorly manifested, where an important category is children with hearing impairments. The process of the place of each of us in society, when and under what conditions it appears, the psychological mechanisms of our integration into society are referred to in psychology as socialization or socialization. There are a number of definitions regarding the implementation, below is an explanation of several of them.

We know that there are different approaches and different definitions of socialization. Below we will consider several of them.

The concept of socialization (given in some literature as socialization) is one of the socio-psychological, sociological, pedagogical categories, a process in which the term expresses the degree to which an individual tends or assimilates existing experiences in society under the influence of the external social environment that surrounds him. Under the general meaning of this concept, it is understood that an individual is born and grows up under the influence of the primary and secondary environment that surrounds him, after which he joins society, applies all his learned experiences in the process of cooperation with those around him, and becomes a tool in transmitting these experiences to someone.

Socialization is the process by which a person acquires social experience, actively remaining it in the process of life and activity. In simple terms, socialization is the process by which each individual can demonstrate it in each act and treatment, and, if necessary, teach the same social experience to others, in turn, while adopting the norms, requirements, expectations and influences of the individual.

The most common of the definitions given to the word positivity (lat. Socialis-Social, Collective) is the individual's ability to penetrate into society and master the qualifications, roles, norms and values that will be necessary for life in it. In the process of interaction, social qualities, knowledge, skills are formed in humans, which are necessary for the participant of communication in society to be able to.

In modern psychology, two other synonyms of the term positivity are widely used: that is, these are the process of "personality formation" and "upbringing". Socialization is also expressed through concepts such as "the penetration of individuality into society", "the assimilation of social influences", and "their use in the process of social communication". Socialization is a process that consists in the fact that we integrate into society and assimilate the social experiences that exist in that society.

This process takes place through three phases of individual social experience:

Accept, absorb;

Application in the process of his own life, activity, attitude;

Transmission to others is the process of being able to exert its influence.

Different psychological scientific schools have analyzed the process of adaptation in different ways:

Neobehaviorism manifestations of positivity is social learning;

Representatives of interactionism the result of social interactions;

Representatives of humanistic psychology, on the other hand, described it as a manifestation of the "I" Concept. Socialization is a lush process, and the opinions presented above by the figures of scientific schools of psychology make the main emphasis only on one side of it. Currently, world psychologists are trying to consider the problem of socialization from the point of view of the dispositional concept of social behavior management. The concept encompasses a

hierarchy of dispositions that analyze the boigan social behavior management system, which depends on the degree to which individuals can access interpersonal relationships. The author of the term "socialization" is the American sociologist F. G. Applied to man by Gulbins, he used it in 1887 in his book "The Theory of socialization" in a sense close to modernity – "the development of the social nature or character of man, the preparation of human materials for social life."

Today, the problem of socialization is studied by philosophers, ethnographers, sociologists, psychologists, etc. In recent decades, the study of socialization has come to maturity and even old age.

Scientists explain the concept of socialization in different ways, mainly adhering to two approaches that differ in understanding the role of an individual in the process of socialization (it should be noted that such a division is conditional).

The first approach involves the passive position of a person in the process of socialization, and considers that socialization itself is a process of adaptation to society, which forms each of its members in accordance with a specific culture. This approach can be called Object-object (society is the subject of interaction and man is its object). The origin of this approach was Scientists: the Frenchman Emil Durkheim and the American Talcott Parsons.

The latter is based on the fact that a person actively participates in the process of socialization and not only adapts to society, but also affects his life circumstances and himself. This approach can be defined as a subject. The founders of this approach can be considered Americans Charles Cooley and George Herbert mida. Socialization is seen as the development and self-transformation of a person in the process of assimilation and reproduction of culture, which occurs in the interaction of a person with life conditions at all age stages, which are self-directed, relatively directed and purposefully created.

The essence of socialization is that in its process a person is formed as a member of the society to which he belongs. In any society, the socialization of a person has its own characteristics.

The peculiarity of human adaptation is that this process involves an active participation in both consumption and transmission, associated with the socialization of the individual, his growth into the social world, the norms and values of social significance of the existing and past social environment. The concept of socialization characterizes the ability of a person to absorb changing conditions, its adaptive essence.

Students with disabilities in the educational process face the following problems:

- decrease in efficiency, change of focus, weakness of mnemonistic processes;
- adequate development of programming and control functions; visual and semi-cosmic difficulties;
- difficulties of hearing and visual information processing.

To solve problems that arise in education, a system of mitigation, correction, support of their impact is required, which in turn offers disabled students a special approach to the process of professional training. In this regard, the issue of support for this category of persons in educational institutions engaged in professional training, in particular, socio-pedagogical support, is very acute. Along with integrated education in education, the essence of the Escort is to maximally reveal the potential opportunities of the student's personality, to promote the full development of the individual and professionally, to create conditions for the full and maximum manifestation of the positive aspects of the personality. The main stages of socio-pedagogical support:

Stage 1-the organization and conduct of diagnostics (psychological, pedagogical) and surveys of students with limited opportunities to develop recommendations in order to improve the results of educational and educational activities.

Stage 2-analysis of the data obtained. Based on the analysis, it is determined that students need psychological and pedagogical support, social support.

Stage 3 - development of recommendations.

Stage 4-psychological-pedagogical consultation.

Stage 5-activity.

Implementation of the developed decisions to eliminate the socio-psychological problems present in students and the plan for providing assistance in the educational process. Stage 6-analysis of support activities. in the organization of comprehensive socio-pedagogical support in the conditions of integrated education with healthy peers in an educational institution, students with disabilities pay special attention, receive pedagogical support and, as specialists, are sincerely interested in integrating into society in a socially and psychologically acceptable way as individuals. . In order to introduce this educational system, it is first necessary to adapt the society, both healthy children in school and children with disabilities to this. Especially children studying in the elementary school do not know what disability is, how not to laugh at such children. That is why when they are observed during inclusive education, such as laughing, ridiculing, isolating, humiliating a peer with a disability, it will certainly have a serious impact on the psyche of a child with a disability. Feeling humiliated among healthy children is a reason for the child to live under constant mental strain. In special boarding schools, however, in the process of education and upbringing of children who are similar in terms of disability, excessive mental pressures are not observed even because their peers around them are similar to themselves, suffer from such a disease as it, and they do not feel weak and weak from those around them.

The socialization of a person as a continuous process of development, and the self-development of an individual is inextricably linked with social adaptation.

In fact, social adaptation is the most important mechanism, a specific form of human socialization.

To understand social adaptation, It is necessary to consider its structure. The logic of the construction of the structure of adaptation is as follows: the subject of adaptation in the first place, it is the main, depending on all other elements of the structure and is built in relation to it. The subject of adaptation has internal parameters that determine its existence and development - are needs. The world around them, in which needs are reflected, is objectified. Anything that stimulates (or hinders) satisfy them - Factors of adaptation. Factors adaptations in the world that surrounds the subject, as well as the subject of adaptation. The environment has its own integral structure and is not the opposite of the subject, therefore, adaptation factors are "dissolved" in it, they are contained in its integral structural components - objects of adaptation. If the needs are inseparable from the subject of adaptation, then the factors are inseparable from the objects of adaptation. For example, residents of the whole country are advised to learn sign speech (Sweden), or each child with hearing impairment who is studying in a public school must have a personal assistant-a sign translator (USA, etc.), certain requirements are imposed. It has been proposed for articulation of all people who are in constant contact with such and hearing-impaired people (specialists, relatives, friends, servants, etc.): their speech should be slow, their articulation should

be exaggerated (Switzerland, Germany, etc.). There are even mock – ups of the "land of the deaf" – for example, a campus where deaf youth live (USA, Gallaudet University) .

In the processes of socialization, the experience of the early stages of ontogenesis, associated with the formation of psychic functions and early forms of social behavior, is decisive; the transfer of social experience through the educational and educational system; and, finally, the interaction of people in the process of communication and joint activities. In the process of socialization, the individual is formed as a member of the society to which he belongs.

Successful socialization is part of life conflicts that prevent not only the effective adaptation of a person to society, but also the ability to resist society to a certain extent, its development and self-realization. Modern society in one way or another produces two types of victims of socialization: a person fully adapted in society, but not capable of resisting it, and a person who is not adapted in society, resisting it.

Therefore, the subject of adaptation is forced to interact with real existing objects of adaptation, the value of which is determined by the presence and severity of adaptation factors for the subject.

In conclusion, the first chapter of our research on socialization and factors affecting it, methodological issues of the psychology of foster children of the House of kindness, their features of psychic development is presented. We have also touched on the theories of domestic and foreign scientists about how to focus on the educational aspects of children with disabilities, what should be paid attention to their socialization, intellectual development, as well as their access to social attitudes and communication. It will not be a mistake if we say that this will serve as one of the main guidelines for future professionals. The problems of social adaptation and rehabilitation of children with disabilities are solved in the conditions of targeted socio-pedagogical impact by introducing them into favorable areas of household, individual and socially significant activities, taking into account the personal interests and capabilities of children.

REFERENCES

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Farmoni, 28.01.2022 yildagi PF-60-son.
2. Mudrik, A.V. Sotsialnaya pedagogika. A.V. Mudrik. – M., 2002 – 378s.
3. Gulbahor Abdullajonovna Nabiyeva. "Imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarning ta'lim-tarbiya olishlari" Scientific progress, vol. 1, no. 5, 2021, pp. 368-372
4. Kristin Snoddon - American sign language and early literacy - Gallaudet University Press , 2012
5. Камолова, Ш. Ў., & Мунарова, Р. Ў. (2010). Уровни совершенство личности. Исследователь научный журнал.–Қозоғистон, 5(49), 100-105.
6. Saidov, A., & Saydullaev, J. (2022). УЗБЕК ОИЛАЛАРИДАГИ ТАРБИЯНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ-ПСИХОЛОГИК АХАМИЯТИ. Science and innovation, 7(B8), 1649-1654.
7. Ismailovich, A. S. (2020). Problems Of Improving Psychology Of Healthy Lifestyle Of Uzbek Family. Scientific reports of Bukhara State University, 4(1), 313-318.
8. SharifjonTo'lqino'g A. et al. TA'LIM-TARBIYA TIZIMI VA O'QITUVCHILAR FAOLIYATIDA PSIXOLOGIK XIZMATNING AHAMIYATI //MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH. – 2022. –T. 1. –No. 11. –С. 57-60.